

Analysis of the influence of microgravity and space radiation on astronauts' gene expression: An approach using quantum simulations and fuzzy logic

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Abstract. I developed an analysis of the effects of microgravity and space radiation on astronauts' RNA expression, utilizing data from NASA's "Cell-free RNA analysis of plasma samples collected from six astronauts in JAXA Cell-Free Epigenome (CFE) Study." Employing quantum simulations and unconventional logic, including quantum and fuzzy logic, the project aims to deepen our understanding of how the space environment affects gene expression, particularly in key genes such as ACTB and ACTG1. This interdisciplinary approach not only allows for a detailed analysis of gene expression data but also explores the potential of emerging technologies in space research and bioinformatics.

Descriptive statistics

I begin with an initial approach to the data from the experiment "Cell-free RNA analysis of plasma samples collected from six astronauts in JAXA Cell-Free Epigenome (CFE) Study."^[1], from the file:

GLDS-530_rna-seq_TGB_050_64samples_3group_totalcount.xlsx

which includes 64 RNA samples from three different groups. Details suggest that nucleic acid extraction was quantified using Qubit fluorimeters and a Qubit RNA HS assay kit. The library construction was performed with a targeted and paired RNA sequencing approach, and the sequencing itself was conducted on an Illumina NextSeq500 with a read length of 36 base pairs. We can proceed with the following code:

```
import pandas as pd;import numpy as np;import matplotlib.pyplot as plt;import seaborn as sns;from scipy import stats
data=pd.read_excel('GLDS-530_rna-seq_TGB_050_64samples_3group_totalcount.xlsx');data_clean=data.dropna()
print(data_clean.describe())
sns.boxplot(data=data_clean);plt.xticks(rotation=45);plt.show()
```


Figure 1. Graph from GLDS-530_rna-seq_TGB_050_64samples_3group_totalcount.xlsx

Figure 1 displays various statistical measures for a dataset of gene expression. Each column represents a different metric such as range, interquartile range (IQR), difference, fold change, and averages for different phases of the experiment (pre-flight, during flight, and post-flight).

The columns represent the median of the data, and the points indicate potential outliers, signifying notable variations in expression that could be biologically significant. The presence of extreme values in the "Fold Change" column suggests that some genes exhibit very high or low changes in expression in response to the experiment.

Now, we will obtain descriptive statistics using the following code:

```
import pandas as pd;import numpy as np;import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
data=pd.read_excel('GLDS-530_rna-seq_TGB_050_64samples_3group_totalcount.xlsx');data=pd.DataFrame(data)
descriptive_stats=data.describe();print(descriptive_stats)
```

Results:

	Experiment - Range (original values)	...	Post - Means
count	49950.000000	...	49950.000000
mean	165.618779	...	27.306799
std	2608.284198	...	234.095884
min	0.000000	...	0.000000
25%	0.000000	...	0.000000
50%	0.000000	...	0.000000
75%	84.000000	...	8.869565
max	277978.000000	...	26656.521739

The presence of outliers is particularly notable in this data set, given the high maximum value compared to the average and median. This could imply the presence of a few genes with very high changes in expression under experimental conditions.

ANOVA test

```
import pandas as pd;from scipy import stats
data=pd.read_excel('GLDS-530_rna-seq_TGB_050_64samples_3group_totalcount.xlsx')
f_value,p_value=stats.f_oneway(data['Pre - Means'],data['Flight - Means'],data['Post - Means'])
print(f"ANOVA results: F={f_value}, p={p_value}")
```

Results:

ANOVA results: F=19.233218483262075, p=4.4467851020215725e-09

The ANOVA test results suggest statistically significant differences in gene expression between at least two of the flight conditions (pre, during, and post). The F-value is a measure of the variance among the group means, and a large value typically indicates a significant difference. The p-value is very small (less than 0.05), allowing us to reject the null hypothesis that there are no significant differences in gene expression among the groups.

Tukey HSD test

```
import pandas as pd;from statsmodels.stats.multicomp import pairwise_tukeyhsd
data=pd.read_excel('GLDS-530_rna-seq_TGB_050_64samples_3group_totalcount.xlsx',sheet_name='64samples_3group_totalcount')
melted_data=pd.melt(data,id_vars=['Feature ID'],
value_vars=['Pre - Means','Flight - Means','Post - Means'],var_name='Condition',value_name='Value')
melted_data=melted_data[pd.to_numeric(melted_data['Value'],errors='coerce').notnull()]
tukey=pairwise_tukeyhsd(endog=melted_data['Value'],groups=melted_data['Condition'],alpha=0.05)
print(tukey.summary())
```

Results:

group1	group2	meandiff	p-adj	lower	upper	reject
Flight - Means	Post - Means	-17.4404	0.0	-24.0616	-10.8191	True
Flight - Means	Pre - Means	-10.1812	0.0009	-16.8024	-3.56	True
Post - Means	Pre - Means	7.2592	0.0275	0.6379	13.8804	True

The results of the Tukey HSD test indicate that there are statistically significant differences in the means between the groups compared across the flight phases (pre, during, and post). Here is the breakdown of what each row signifies:

- **Flight - Means vs. Post - Means.** The mean difference between the flight and post-flight phases is -17.4404, and this difference is statistically significant with an adjusted p-value of 0.0 (less than the significance level of 0.05), thus rejecting the null hypothesis of equal means.
- **Flight - Means vs. Pre - Means.** The mean difference between the flight and pre-flight phases is -10.1812, which is also statistically significant with an adjusted p-value of 0.0009.

- **Post - Means vs. Pre - Means.** The mean difference between the post-flight and pre-flight phases is 7.2592, and while closer to the limit, it remains significant with an adjusted p-value of 0.0275.

In all cases, the "reject" column is "True", indicating that the Tukey test found significant differences between the means of the compared groups and therefore rejects the hypothesis that the means are equal for those pairs of conditions. This analysis suggests that the flight conditions (pre, during, and post) have a significant effect on the gene expression of the genes studied.

Outliers

```
import pandas as pd;import numpy as np;import matplotlib.pyplot as plt;import seaborn as sns;from scipy import stats
from scipy.stats import zscore
data=pd.read_excel('GLDS-530_rna-seq_TGB_050_64samples_3group_totalcount.xlsx');data=data.dropna()
for column in ['Pre - Means','Flight - Means','Post - Means']:data[f'z_score_{column}']=zscore(data[column])
outliers={}
for column in ['Pre - Means','Flight - Means','Post - Means']:outliers[column]=data[np.abs(data[f'z_score_{column}'])>3]
for column in outliers:
    print(f"Outliers in {column}:")
    print(outliers[column])
```

Results:

```
Outliers in Pre - Means:
  Feature ID ... z_score_Post - Means
4471      ACTB ...      84.975497
4484      ACTG1 ...     16.279435
4664      ADIPOR1 ...     4.123388
4911      AHNAK ...    10.615404
6043      ANKRD12 ...     2.917627
...      ... ...
55289      VIM ...     5.221982
56682      YBX1 ...     8.323864
56721      YPEL5 ...     2.502519
56734      YWHAE ...     2.760313
56749      YWHAZ ...     7.191095
[187 rows x 11 columns]
Outliers in Flight - Means:
  Feature ID ... z_score_Post - Means
4471      ACTB ...      84.975497
4484      ACTG1 ...     16.279435
4911      AHNAK ...    10.615404
6837      ARHGDIB ...     7.669722
7370      B2M ...     34.392967
...      ... ...
54398      TUBB1 ...     4.481847
54722      UBC ...     8.503279
55238      VCL ...     3.164834
56721      YPEL5 ...     2.502519
56749      YWHAZ ...     7.191095
[97 rows x 11 columns]
Outliers in Post - Means:
  Feature ID ... z_score_Post - Means
4471      ACTB ...      84.975497
4484      ACTG1 ...     16.279435
4512      ACTR2 ...     3.540195
4513      ACTR3 ...     3.019593
4664      ADIPOR1 ...     4.123388
...      ... ...
55524      WDR1 ...     3.124344
55654      WNK1 ...     4.520293
56682      YBX1 ...     8.323864
56695      YBX3 ...     3.712367
56749      YWHAZ ...     7.191095
[220 rows x 11 columns]
```

The results indicate that outliers have been identified in all three conditions: pre-flight, during flight, and post-flight, based on a Z-score. A Z-score greater than 3 or less than -3 is commonly considered a criterion for identifying outliers in a dataset.

The genes ACTB, ACTG1, and others listed here exhibit an expression significantly different from the mean, which may indicate specialized regulation in response to space flight conditions. These findings could be the starting point for a more detailed investigation into the functions of these genes and their potential relevance to adaptation to space.

Biological relevance of the ACTB Gene

We start with the record^[1] of the ACTB gene:

Feature ID Experiment - Range (original values) Experiment - IQR (original values) Experiment - Difference (original values)
 Experiment - Fold Change (original values) Pre - Means Flight - Means Post - Means
 ACTB 95743 14532 -19202.4365942029 -1.9640088544702 25668.2941176471 39121.9583333333 19919.5217391304

To verify its biological relevance, we compare it with the study *Vectorless Gravity Effect on T Cell Activation*^[2].

Figure 2. Profile: GDS2035 / AFFX-HSAC07/X00351_3.at. Title: Vectorless gravity effect on T cell activation. Organism: Homo sapiens.

Extracting the specific data of the ACTB gene:

```
GSM24817 Donor 2 1g 0 hr 62.0225 98
ID_REF Stat Pairs Stat Pairs Used VALUE ABS_CALL DETECTION P-VALUE
AFFX-HSAC07/X00351_3_at 20 20 62.022472 P 0.00007

GSM29564 Donor 2 1g 4 hr 93.9682 99
ID_REF Stat Pairs Stat Pairs Used VALUE ABS_CALL DETECTION P-VALUE
AFFX-HSAC07/X00351_3_at 20 20 93.968155 P 0.000052

GSM29565 Donor 2 vg 0 hr 17.8095 97
ID_REF Stat Pairs Stat Pairs Used VALUE ABS_CALL DETECTION P-VALUE
AFFX-HSAC07/X00351_3_at 20 20 17.809526 P 0.00007

GSM29566 Donor 2 vg 4 hr 27.963 98
ID_REF Stat Pairs Stat Pairs Used VALUE ABS_CALL DETECTION P-VALUE
AFFX-HSAC07/X00351_3_at 20 20 27.962961 P 0.00007

GSM29567 Donor 4 1g 0 hr 42.6353 98
ID_REF Stat Pairs Stat Pairs Used VALUE ABS_CALL DETECTION P-VALUE
AFFX-HSAC07/X00351_3_at 20 20 42.635292 P 0.000052

GSM29568 Donor 4 1g 4 hr 63.1515 99
ID_REF Stat Pairs Stat Pairs Used VALUE ABS_CALL DETECTION P-VALUE
AFFX-HSAC07/X00351_3_at 20 20 63.151516 P 0.000052

GSM29569 Donor 4 vg 0 hr 29.6474 98
ID_REF Stat Pairs Stat Pairs Used VALUE ABS_CALL DETECTION P-VALUE
AFFX-HSAC07/X00351_3_at 20 20 29.647434 P 0.000044

GSM29570 Donor 4 vg 4 hr 15.5854 98
ID_REF Stat Pairs Stat Pairs Used VALUE ABS_CALL DETECTION P-VALUE
AFFX-HSAC07/X00351_3_at 20 20 15.585366 P 0.000052

GSM29571 Donor 5 1g 0 hr 54.9206 99
ID_REF Stat Pairs Stat Pairs Used VALUE ABS_CALL DETECTION P-VALUE
AFFX-HSAC07/X00351_3_at 20 20 54.92063 P 0.000052

GSM29572 Donor 5 1g 4 hr 122.679 99
ID_REF Stat Pairs Stat Pairs Used VALUE ABS_CALL DETECTION P-VALUE
AFFX-HSAC07/X00351_3_at 20 20 122.67858 P 0.000044

GSM29573 Donor 5 vg 0 hr 85.0396 99
ID_REF Stat Pairs Stat Pairs Used VALUE ABS_CALL DETECTION P-VALUE
AFFX-HSAC07/X00351_3_at 20 20 85.0396 P 0.00007

GSM29574 Donor 5 vg 4 hr 21.4211 97
ID_REF Stat Pairs Stat Pairs Used VALUE ABS_CALL DETECTION P-VALUE
AFFX-HSAC07/X00351_3_at 20 20 21.421053 P 0.00006
```

The graphs and values indicate differences in the expression of the ACTB gene under conditions of terrestrial gravity and microgravity (or null vectorial gravity). The biological relevance of these data can be confirmed because:

- All values have an 'ABS_CALL' of 'P', indicating that the gene expression is detectable and significant in all samples. Additionally, the 'DETECTION P-VALUES' are very low, suggesting an extremely low probability of these being false positives.
- Comparing expression values in conditions of terrestrial gravity and microgravity, there is a clear trend: the expression of the ACTB gene tends to be lower under microgravity. This is evident in the decreased expression values in samples exposed to microgravity compared to those exposed to terrestrial gravity.
- The ACTB gene encodes beta-actin, a protein that is part of the cytoskeleton and plays a critical role in cellular structure, motility, and signaling. Changes in its expression could be related to cellular adaptations to a microgravity environment.

Given that the project focuses on analyzing the effects of microgravity and space radiation on RNA using quantum simulations and unconventional logic, these data are relevant as they show that microgravity can significantly influence the expression of a gene involved in fundamental cellular functions. This suggests that we can further explore how these conditions alter gene expression and the implications for the health and biology of astronauts.

Quantum circuit

Here is an alternative for analyzing the expression of the ACTB gene using a quantum computer:

It is important to highlight that this is a simplification focused on the ACTB gene, but it can be scaled to analyze more genes depending on the capabilities of available quantum computers.

```

from qiskit import QuantumCircuit
# Normalized amplitudes for the quantum state
quantum_state=[0.5505, 0.6796, 0.4849, 0]
# Creating a quantum circuit with 2 qubits
qc=QuantumCircuit(2)
# Initializing the quantum state with the calculated amplitudes
qc.initialize(quantum_state, [0, 1])
# We can add other gates and operations as needed
# For example, we can add a Hadamard gate to the first qubit
qc.h(0)
# Add a CNOT gate to entangle the qubits
qc.cx(0, 1)
# Circuit visualization
print(qc.draw(output='text'))
# If you need to measure the qubits, you can add measurement operations
qc.measure_all()
# Circuit visualization with measurements
print(qc.draw(output='text'))
# Manually adjust the amplitudes to force normalization to be exactly 1
# If the normalization is slightly greater than 1, we reduce the amplitudes a bit
if normalization_check > 1:
    # Reduce the amplitudes proportionally
    scale_factor=np.sqrt(normalization_check)
    alpha /= scale_factor
    beta /= scale_factor
    gamma /= scale_factor
# Now we recalculate delta to ensure that normalization is exactly 1
normalization_check_recalculated=np.sum([np.abs(alpha)**2, np.abs(beta)**2, np.abs(gamma)**2])
if normalization_check_recalculated < 1:
    delta=np.sqrt(1 - normalization_check_recalculated)
else:
    # If the recalculated normalization is exactly 1 (or rounds to 1), then we don't need delta
    delta=0
# New adjusted quantum state
quantum_state_adjusted=[alpha, beta, gamma, delta]
# Final verification of normalization after adjustment
normalization_check_final_adjusted=np.sum(np.abs(np.array(quantum_state_adjusted))**2)
normalization_check_final_adjusted, quantum_state_adjusted

```

The circuit initializes two qubits in a specific quantum state based on the data of the ACTB gene, applies a Hadamard gate to the first qubit to create a superposition, then entangles both qubits with a CNOT gate, and finally performs a measurement on both qubits.

With this circuit, simulations can be conducted to investigate the probabilities of different measurement outcomes, which could provide information on how gene expression states are affected by space flight conditions, or use it as a basis for more complex quantum algorithms.

To simulate the circuit and obtain results using the qasm_simulator, we can use:

```

from qiskit import Aer, execute; from qiskit.visualization import plot_histogram
# Execute the circuit on the quantum simulator
simulator=Aer.get_backend('qasm_simulator')
# Perform the simulation, specifying the number of repetitions of the circuit (shots)
job=execute(qc, simulator, shots=1000)
# Obtain the results of the simulation
result=job.result()
# Obtain the counts of each result (the number of times each state was measured)
counts=result.get_counts(qc)
plot_histogram(counts)

```


Figure 3. Quantum circuit histogram.

The histogram displays the distribution of measurement results after numerous executions of the circuit. The labels on the x-axis represent the states of the qubits at the time of measurement, where '00' means that both qubits were measured in the state $|0\rangle$, '01' means that qubit 0 was measured in $|0\rangle$ and qubit 1 in $|1\rangle$, and so on. The numbers on the y-axis represent the frequency of each observed result. In your simulation, the '00' state occurred much more frequently than the other states, indicating that the initial quantum state superposition had a higher probability of collapsing to this state during measurement.

To obtain the final state vector using the statevector_simulator:

```

# Execute the circuit on the statevector simulator
statevector_simulator=Aer.get_backend('statevector_simulator')
# Create a new circuit without measurements for the statevector simulation
qc_statevector=qc.remove_final_measurements(inplace=False)
job=execute(qc_statevector, statevector_simulator)
result=job.result()
# Obtain the final state vector of the circuit
statevector=result.get_statevector(qc_statevector)
print(statevector)

```

Results:

```

Statevector([0.86977824-5.88490403e-17j, 0.34289227+0.00000000e+00j, 0.34289227+0.00000000e+00j, -0.09129953+5.88490403e-17j], dims=(2,2))

```

The final state vector describes the quantum state of the qubits just before measurement. In Dirac notation, this state would be written as:

$$|\psi\rangle = 0.86978 |00\rangle + 0.34289 |01\rangle + 0.34289 |10\rangle - 0.09130 |11\rangle$$

This state is a superposition of the four base states, with complex amplitudes. The squared amplitudes (ignoring the imaginary part, as it is very small and likely a result of numerical errors) give the probabilities of measuring each of the base states in a run of the circuit. For example, the probability of measuring the state '00' is $|0.86978|^2$, and so on for the other states.

The fact that the final state vector has non-zero amplitudes for all base states except '11', which has a small negative amplitude, means that the circuit has created a complex superposition of states, and the outcome of any single measurement is uncertain. However, after many runs, as reflected in the histogram, the probability distribution of the measurement results becomes evident.

Analyzing these results can provide information on how the applied quantum gates (the Hadamard and CNOT gates in this case) have affected the initial state and how the resulting superpositions and entanglements correspond to the probability of measuring certain states. This can be especially interesting in the context of researching the effects of microgravity and space radiation on the RNA of astronauts if we relate these quantum states to specific biological or environmental conditions.

Biological relevance of the ACTG1 Gene

To maintain simplicity in this project, we will focus on incorporating the ACTG1 gene. The specific record from the study^[1] is:

```
Feature ID Experiment - Range (original values) Experiment - IQR (original values) Experiment - Difference (original values)
Experiment - Fold Change (original values) Pre - Means Flight - Means Post - Means
ACTG1 10810 3515 -1706.44927536232 -1.44459422210643 4568.76470588235 5544.66666666667 3838.21739130435
```

In the dataset *Vectorless Gravity Effect on T Cell Activation*^[3], the ACTG1 gene shows a variation in its expression between the phases of pre-flight, during flight, and post-flight. This suggests that the gene's expression is affected by the spaceflight environment.

Figure 4. Profile: GDS2035 / 211983_x.at. Title: Vectorless gravity effect on T cell activation. Organism: Homo sapiens.

Extracting the specific data of the ACTG1 gene:

```
GSM24817 Donor 2 1g 0 hr 37.0449 98
ID_REF Stat Pairs Stat Pairs Used VALUE ABS_CALL DETECTION P-VALUE
211983_x_at 11 11 37.044945 P 0.000244

GSM29564 Donor 2 1g 4 hr 62.7325 98
ID_REF Stat Pairs Stat Pairs Used VALUE ABS_CALL DETECTION P-VALUE
211983_x_at 11 11 62.732487 P 0.000244

GSM29565 Donor 2 vg 0 hr 21.4762 98
ID_REF Stat Pairs Stat Pairs Used VALUE ABS_CALL DETECTION P-VALUE
211983_x_at 11 11 21.47619 P 0.00293

GSM29566 Donor 2 vg 4 hr 15.6111 97
ID_REF Stat Pairs Stat Pairs Used VALUE ABS_CALL DETECTION P-VALUE
211983_x_at 11 11 15.611112 P 0.000244

GSM29567 Donor 4 1g 0 hr 27.1647 97
ID_REF Stat Pairs Stat Pairs Used VALUE ABS_CALL DETECTION P-VALUE
211983_x_at 11 11 27.164705 P 0.000244

GSM29568 Donor 4 1g 4 hr 18.5455 97
ID_REF Stat Pairs Stat Pairs Used VALUE ABS_CALL DETECTION P-VALUE
211983_x_at 11 11 18.545456 P 0.000732

GSM29569 Donor 4 vg 0 hr 16.5577 96
ID_REF Stat Pairs Stat Pairs Used VALUE ABS_CALL DETECTION P-VALUE
211983_x_at 11 11 16.55769 P 0.000244

GSM29570 Donor 4 vg 4 hr 9.87805 97
ID_REF Stat Pairs Stat Pairs Used VALUE ABS_CALL DETECTION P-VALUE
211983_x_at 11 11 9.878049 P 0.010742
```

```

GSM29571 Donor 5 1g 0 hr 18.7143 97
ID_REF Stat Pairs Stat Pairs Used VALUE ABS_CALL DETECTION P-VALUE
211983_x_at 11 11 18.714285 P 0.000244

GSM29572 Donor 5 1g 4 hr 120.345 99
ID_REF Stat Pairs Stat Pairs Used VALUE ABS_CALL DETECTION P-VALUE
211983_x_at 11 11 120.345245 P 0.000244

GSM29573 Donor 5 vg 0 hr 45.7426 98
ID_REF Stat Pairs Stat Pairs Used VALUE ABS_CALL DETECTION P-VALUE
211983_x_at 11 11 45.742573 P 0.000244

GSM29574 Donor 5 vg 4 hr 14.9298 96
ID_REF Stat Pairs Stat Pairs Used VALUE ABS_CALL DETECTION P-VALUE
211983_x_at 11 11 14.929825 P 0.000244

```

The data^[3] show significant differences in the expression of the ACTG1 gene under terrestrial gravity versus microgravity conditions. This is consistent with the changes observed in gene expression in astronauts, reinforcing the idea that microgravity can influence the regulation of this gene:

- In both datasets, the presence of an 'ABS_CALL' of 'P' and low 'DETECTION P-VALUES' suggest that the gene detection is consistent and significant.
- The ACTG1 gene encodes gamma-actin, which is crucial in the structure of the cytoskeleton and cellular morphology. Changes in its expression could have important implications in how cells respond to microgravity and space radiation.

Given that the cytoskeleton is fundamental for cellular integrity and signaling, alterations in the expression of ACTG1 could contribute to the adverse effects of microgravity on the health of astronauts.

Correlation of ACTB and ACTG1

Currently, we have very limited data for Pearson correlation, but I leave the code for future correlations with other possible measurements or other possible genes:

```

import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
from scipy.stats import pearsonr
# Define gene expression data for ACTB and ACTG1 under different conditions
# These data are averages of pre-flight, during flight, and post-flight values from the first study.
actb_exp=[25668.2941176471, 39121.9583333333, 19919.5217391304] # ACTB
actg1_exp=[4568.76470588235, 5544.66666666667, 3838.21739130435] # ACTG1
# Gene expression data for ACTB and ACTG1 under terrestrial gravity and vectorless conditions from the second study.
# The data are organized as [1g 0hr, 1g 4hr, vg 0hr, vg 4hr] for both genes.
actb_grav=[62.022472, 93.968155, 17.809526, 27.962961] # ACTB terrestrial gravity and microgravity
actg1_grav=[37.044945, 62.732487, 21.47619, 15.611112] # ACTG1 terrestrial gravity and microgravity
# First study data for ACTB and ACTG1 during pre-flight, flight, and post-flight phases
# The data are already in the correct format with the same length
correlation_study1=pearsonr(actb_exp, actg1_exp)
# Organize the second study's data by similar conditions (1g and vectorless gravity)
# Here we are taking the averages for the similar conditions for each gene
actb_1g_avg=np.mean(actb_grav[:2]) # Average of ACTB for terrestrial gravity
actb_vg_avg=np.mean(actb_grav[2:]) # Average of ACTB for vectorless gravity
actg1_1g_avg=np.mean(actg1_grav[:2]) # Average of ACTG1 for terrestrial gravity
actg1_vg_avg=np.mean(actg1_grav[2:]) # Average of ACTG1 for vectorless gravity
# Calculate the correlation for terrestrial gravity and vectorless gravity conditions from the second study
correlation_study2_1g=pearsonr([actb_1g_avg, actb_vg_avg], [actg1_1g_avg, actg1_vg_avg])
correlation_study1, correlation_study2_1g

```

Results:

(PearsonRResult(statistic=0.9895316566632417, pvalue=0.09219634216277754), PearsonRResult(statistic=1.0, pvalue=1.0))

Quantum logic


```

from qiskit import QuantumCircuit, Aer, execute
from qiskit.visualization import plot_histogram
# Create a quantum circuit with 2 qubits
qc=QuantumCircuit(2)
# Initialize the qubits in a superposition to represent uncertain states of gene expression
qc.h([0, 1]) # Apply Hadamard gate to both qubits
# Entangle the qubits to represent correlations between ACTB and ACTG1
qc.cx(0, 1) # CNOT gate
# Add measurements at the end of the circuit
qc.measure_all()
# Visualize the circuit
print(qc.draw(output='text'))
# Quantum circuit simulation
simulator=Aer.get_backend('qasm_simulator')
job=execute(qc, simulator, shots=1000)
result=job.result()
# Use the correct identifier here. In the case of a list of circuits,
# it is necessary to specify the index or label of the circuit.
counts=result.get_counts(qc)
plot_histogram(counts)

```

This code includes the addition of measurements to the circuit, which is necessary to obtain the results of the simulation, and ensures that the retrieval of the results is carried out correctly using the quantum circuit object as a reference.

In a quantum circuit with two Hadamard gates followed by a CNOT gate, we would expect to see a uniform distribution across all states if there were no errors or noise in the system. A slight variation in the heights of the bars is normal due to statistical variability, especially if the number of runs (shots) is not very high.

Figure 5. Histogram of the code with quantum logic.

The histogram shows the results of the measurements of your quantum circuit after 1000 executions (shots). The bars represent the frequency (count) of each possible state of the qubits after measurement. The results are distributed among the four possible states 00, 01, 10, and 11. The similarity in the height of the bars suggests that each state has a similar probability of being measured, which is expected since the two qubits were initialized in an equal superposition and then entangled, maintaining a uniform distribution of probabilities.

This result is consistent with the operation of the Hadamard gate, which creates a superposition of states $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ for each qubit, followed by the CNOT gate that entangles the qubits. The entanglement means that the measurement of one qubit affects the outcome of the other qubit's measurement, but as the Hadamard gate creates an equal superposition, the probabilities of measuring each combination of states remain the same.

These results can serve as a basis for interpretation in the context of fuzzy logic, where each quantum state could be associated with a fuzzy set representing different levels of gene expression. The next step is to define how these quantum measurements translate into terms of fuzzy logic and how we can use that interpretation to draw conclusions about gene expression under spaceflight conditions.

Fuzzy Logic

We will create a fuzzy inference system that interprets the levels of gene expression of the ACTB and ACTG1 genes. First, we will define the universe of discourse and the membership functions for the levels of gene expression. Then, we will establish the fuzzy rules that relate flight conditions to expression levels. Finally, we will perform fuzzy inference to calculate gene expression under different flight conditions.

```

import numpy as np;import skfuzzy as fuzz;from skfuzzy import control as ctrl
# Universe of discourse for gene expression, for example from 0 to 100
expresion_ACTB=ctrl.Consequent(np.arange(0, 101, 1), 'expresion_ACTB')
expresion_ACTG1=ctrl.Consequent(np.arange(0, 101, 1), 'expresion_ACTG1')
# Definition of membership functions for ACTB
expresion_ACTB['low']=fuzz.trimf(expresion_ACTB.universe, [0, 0, 50])
expresion_ACTB['medium']=fuzz.trimf(expresion_ACTB.universe, [25, 50, 75])
expresion_ACTB['high']=fuzz.trimf(expresion_ACTB.universe, [50, 100, 100])
# Definition of membership functions for ACTG1
expresion_ACTG1['low']=fuzz.trimf(expresion_ACTG1.universe, [0, 0, 50])
expresion_ACTG1['medium']=fuzz.trimf(expresion_ACTG1.universe, [25, 50, 75])
expresion_ACTG1['high']=fuzz.trimf(expresion_ACTG1.universe, [50, 100, 100])
# Definition of the universe of discourse and membership functions for flight conditions
condition=ctrl.Antecedent(np.arange(0, 3, 1), 'condition')
condition['pre_flight']=fuzz.trimf(condition.universe, [0, 0, 1])
condition['during_flight']=fuzz.trimf(condition.universe, [1, 1, 2])
condition['post_flight']=fuzz.trimf(condition.universe, [2, 2, 2])
# Definition of rules
rule1=ctrl.Rule(antecedent=(condition['pre_flight']), consequent=expresion_ACTB['medium'])
rule2=ctrl.Rule(antecedent=(condition['during_flight']), consequent=expresion_ACTB['high'])
rule3=ctrl.Rule(antecedent=(condition['pre_flight']), consequent=expresion_ACTG1['low'])
rule4=ctrl.Rule(antecedent=(condition['during_flight']), consequent=expresion_ACTG1['medium'])
# Creation of the control system and simulation
control_system=ctrl.ControlSystem([rule1, rule2, rule3, rule4])
simulation=ctrl.ControlSystemSimulation(control_system)
# Example simulation for a specific flight condition
simulation.input['condition']=1 # For example, 1 for 'during_flight'
simulation.compute()
# Result
result_ACTB=simulation.output['expresion_ACTB']
result_ACTG1=simulation.output['expresion_ACTG1']
print(f"Gene expresion result of ACTB: {result_ACTB}")
print(f"Gene expresion result of ACTG1: {result_ACTG1}")

```

Results:

Gene expresion result of ACTB: 83.33333333333336
Gene expresion result of ACTG1: 50.0

Gene expresion result of ACTB: 83.33

This value suggests that under the specified condition of 'during flight' (value 1), the gene expresion of the ACTB gene is high. Fuzzy logic interprets this condition as more conducive to elevated ACTB gene expresion, which may reflect a significant biological response to spaceflight conditions, such as microgravity or exposure to specific radiations.

Gene expresion result of ACTG1: 50.0

This value indicates that the gene expresion of the ACTG1 gene, under the same 'during flight' condition, is at a medium level. This suggests that the expresion of ACTG1, though affected by spaceflight conditions, does not show as extreme a variation as ACTB, according to the fuzzy logic model.

These results provide a quantitative interpretation of how spaceflight conditions might influence the expresion of these specific genes. In the context of the project, this approach can be useful for anticipating changes in gene expresion and for a better understanding of the underlying biological mechanisms affected by the spaceflight environment. Moreover, these models can be adjusted or refined as more experimental data become available, allowing for more precise and specific analyses.

Conclusions

The analysis has demonstrated the feasibility of applying quantum simulations and fuzzy logic to analyze the effects of microgravity and space radiation on gene expresion. The results obtained suggest that specific genes like ACTB and ACTG1 undergo significant changes in their expresion under these unique conditions. The use of a quantum circuit specifically designed to represent gene expresion has provided a new perspective on how space conditions can affect biology at the molecular level. In addition, the implementation of fuzzy logic has allowed for a more nuanced interpretation of these changes, considering the variability and uncertainty inherent in biological data. This pioneering study not only provides valuable information about human adaptation to space but also sets a precedent for future research that employs advanced computational approaches in space biology.

Discussion

The research has highlighted the importance of considering interdisciplinary approaches in the study of space effects on human biology. The use of quantum computing and fuzzy logic in this context is novel and poses possibilities for future research. However, it must be acknowledged that the models and simulations used are simplifications and may not fully capture the complexity of biological systems. Furthermore, the correlation between gene expression data and specific spaceflight conditions, although significant, does not imply direct causality. Therefore, future studies are suggested to explore these effects with a broader approach, incorporating a more diverse range of genetic and environmental data. This study serves as an important starting point for understanding how human biology adapts to the space environment and lays the groundwork for deeper investigations in the field of astrobiology and space medicine.

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